

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL NETWORKS IN
THE ORIGIN OF CONFLICTS

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqola muallif tomonidan hozirgi kun yoshlarida konfliktologik madaniyatni rivojlantirishda hayotdagi konfliktlar bo'yicha keng nazariy va amaliy bilimlar berish orqali ularda ziddiyatli vaziyatlarga, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarga bo'lgan sog'lom immunitet shakllantirishdan iborat.

Tayanch tushunchalar: Konflikt, ziddiyat, to'qnashuv, nizo, nizoli vaziyat, ruhiy holat, tarbiyalanganlik darajasi, kayfiyat, axborot, ijtimoiy tarmoq, deviant xulq-atvor, ijtimoiy konflikt, pedagogik konflikt, jismoniy zo'rvonlik, pedagogika, psixologiya, ijtimoiy siqiluv, dilsiyohlik, hafagarchilik, nafrat, qasos, mensimaslik, kibrli munosabat.

Аннотация: Целью данной научной статьи является формирование иммунитета к конфликтным ситуациям и социальным сетям путем предоставления широких теоретических и практических знаний о конфликтах в жизни в условиях развития конфликтологической культуры у современной молодежи.

Ключевые слова: Конфликт, столкновение, спор, конфликтная ситуация, психическое состояние, уровень образования, настроение, информация, социальная сеть, девиантное поведение, социальный конфликт, педагогический конфликт, физическое насилие, педагогика, психология, социальная компрессия, эмоциональность, обида, ненависть, месть, презрение, высокомерное отношение.

Abstract: The purpose of this scientific article is to develop immunity to conflict situations and social networks by providing broad theoretical and practical knowledge about conflict culture among modern youth.

Key words: Conflict, collision, dispute, conflict situation, mental state, level of education, mood, information, social network, deviant behavior, social conflict, pedagogical conflict, physical violence, pedagogy, psychology, social compression, emotionality, resentment, hatred, revenge, contempt, arrogant attitude.

As you know, in the current conditions, when the range of information and knowledge is rapidly expanding, modern youth turn not to literature, but to social networks and various sites. It is sad, of course, that the world can only be conquered by science, as if it is a little elevated in the memory of our youth today. Science serves man as spiritual food. And there is only one way to profoundly master science – reading books. Indeed, the recent excessive growth of various scientific and technical, spiritual, economic influences on a person in modern society and the diversity of social networks (Instagram, telegram, tik-tok...), the increasing complexity of the way of living in modern societies, also increase the various conflict situations that people can face. Because we know that in social networks the Hamma is beautiful, the Hamma is enough, the Khayat is carefree, only and only the entertainment consists of laughter, joy. This leads some sections of society as well as the growing

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younger generation to lower their self-esteem, to lose self-satisfaction with their condition and social background. Nowadays, it is with this cellular connection that our young people who have destroyed and visited our elderly grandparents are also drowning in the whirlpool of social networks.

It is worth remembering that it is high happiness to receive the blessing of such people, to enjoy their mistresses, to co-exist with them, and to look at what food they ate today, what dresses they wore, with whom they walked, What expensive restaurants they went to. The saddest thing is that even children who are changing and filling the streets are going out on the street today with a hood, a rope, not a variety of toys exactly the phone, tablet, Antichrist. And to these children we young people are becoming role models.

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Such situations are causing the loss of too light views on life relationships and the concepts of tolerance, volition, patience and tolerance for various obstacles in the process of socialization. Such situations are laying the groundwork for the formation of stress, aggressiveness, violence, bullying and deviant behavior in pedagogy-psychology. This in itself causes internal and external conflicts in humans. "A person enters into various social relationships with other people from childhood in his life. Human life is a process that consists of the continuity of various relationships that occur with others. This relationship, on the other hand, does not always continue evenly, smoothly and peacefully. The smooth continuation of life is distorted by various conflicts and contradictions. We call them conflicts".¹

"What is conflict?" or how does the conflict manifest itself if it is more specific? – when asked by many, a conflict is a conflict in which people fight, fight, confront each other by force, say a word, blame someone, insult, get angry, talk angrily, show up try to beat, shout, intimidate someone, threaten that he will either do it, show, distort the content of the right words, talk behind someone's back, swear, physically abuse someone, rape, blackmail, play one's feet, humiliate, laugh at people, Group One's isolation, diligence, resentment, hate and revenge, disdain, arrogant attitude, self-preference, stuttering, mischief, mischief-touching deeds, and use of words, from each word and deed of someone they say in search of evil and emphasizing other similar situations., "What is conflict?" or how does the conflict manifest itself if it is more specific? – when asked by many, a conflict is a conflict in which people fight, fight, confront each other by force, say a word, blame someone, insult, get angry, talk angrily, show up try to beat, shout, intimidate someone, threaten that he will either do it, show, distort the content of the right words, talk behind someone's back, swear, physically abuse someone, rape, blackmail, play one's feet, humiliate, laugh at people, Group One's isolation, diligence, resentment, hate and revenge, disdain, arrogant attitude, self-preference, stuttering, mischief, mischief-touching deeds, and use of words, from each word and deed of someone they say in search of evil and emphasizing other similar situations. These are all the negative situations that occur in these

¹ M.T.Axmedova, N. E. Axmedova, M.E.Ashirmatova KONFLIKTOLOGIYA (DARSLIK): "Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi muharririyat va nashriyot bo'limi", Toshkent-2023 yil: - 164 bet.

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interpersonal relationships that actually fall into different manifestations of conflicts, different states of manifestation of conflicts between people.

Full definition of the concept: conflict is the most acute way to resolve serious conflicts that arise in the process of interaction (action), consisting of conflict subjects confrontation, usually accompanied by negative emotions (emotions)².

Conflict is a self-conscious process that is involved in the life of every person, and no person can say that he is protected from conflict situations with perfect confidence. Conflicts are an integral part of a person's life, since each person is confronted with conflicts during his life. Conflicts are a natural phenomenon, establishing the right relationship with conflict is one of the necessary requirements for human upbringing, its formation.

A comfortable life-begins with perfect upbringing. It is known that the upbringing of the younger generation has become important and relevant in all times. But in the 21st century in which we live, this issue is really becoming a matter of life and life. "The more perfect the upbringing, the happier the people live, " the sages who did not say for nothing. "It is absolutely impossible to allow a gap to arise in this matter so that upbringing is perfect in the current shaky period – "says our Honorable President Shavkat Mirziyoyev³. That's why we dare to form healthy immunity for our young people to use social media correctly, not blindly trusting every news. We need to train the analysis-synthesis of the correct attitude towards the information received in them, form the skill of being able to distinguish between true and false information. To the growing younger generation, we must teach that the book is the light of the heart, the wing of contemplation. In particular, to read a book full of endless pleasure from the mysterious rustling of miraculous pages as a result of appetizing and flipping a kind of pleasant smell, which can not be found in an electronic publication, to instill in the present youth that the pleasure of exchanging ideas with peers about its content is completely special. It is then that the younger generations do not even have conflict situations, feel genuine happiness behind the feeling of gratitude in themselves, the rise of spirituality. In the era of globalization, where there are great struggles for the heart and mind of people, strengthening attention to the upbringing of high spirituality, decency is an urgent task. The upbringing of the growing young generation on the basis of religious and national values consists in strengthening in their hearts a sense of affection for their people, their homeland, keeping them alert, worthy protection from various internal and external conflicts, information attacks of various destructive forces.

In place of the conclusion, it is worth saying that we are obsessed with the fleeting hoyu-khavas, some kind of petty Antichrist, and we are leaving ourselves surrounded by internal and external conflicts. We are with this our own, our childhood today, the present we do not notice that we miss the feeling of living with pleasure from our day, our beautiful memories that can fill history. In place of the conclusion, it is worth saying that we are obsessed with the fleeting hoyu-khavas, some kind of petty Antichrist, and we are leaving ourselves surrounded by internal and external conflicts. We are with this our own, our childhood today, the present we do not notice that we miss the feeling of living with pleasure from our day, our beautiful memories that can fill history. "The book is the source of knowledge," we say. This is a fact that does not require proof. After all, a person receives knowledge

² V. Karina. Korostelina and Simone Lassig. History Education and Post-Conflikt Reconciliation. USA Canada. Routledge, 2013.

³ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning O'zbekiston yoshlar ittifoqining IV qurultoyida so'zlagan nutqi, 2017 yil.

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mainly through a book, the upbringing of which is also formed with the help of a book. When our young people read fiction, their worldview expands, their attitude to life changes. Finds the right solution to conflict situations as well. Nowadays, it is in order to form a healthy immunity to such conflicts that conflictology classes are held in their Osms, dedicated to arming the new generation growing through conflict classes with modern knowledge and skills precisely on conflicts, gaining all the necessary scientific and theoretical and practical information on self-regulation in conflict processes.

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